

D6.1 / Project branding and communication channel

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DMT	Data management team
IPR	Intellectual property rights
PsA	Psoriatic Arthritis
PsO	Psoriasis
WHO	World Health Organization
WWW	World Wide Web

Executive summary

The aim of the current document is to provide the project branding and communication channel of the iPROLEPSIS project. More specifically, it includes the project's visual identity, website, social media channels and communication kit of the project.

1 Introduction

This document provides an overview of the project visual identity, website, social media channels and communication kit of the iPROLEPSIS project. More specifically, the project visual identity/brand (logo) with its unique features is presented. The web portal (website) used for the public presentation, communication, and outreach of the iPROLEPSIS project as well as, social media channels and other communication tool are also detailed in the current deliverable.

1.1 Document scope

Deliverable D6.1 is the first deliverable of the WP6 ‘Dissemination, communication and exploitation’ and is part of the Task 6.1 ‘Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring’. WP6 is an integral part of the iPROLEPSIS’ work plan and spans the entire duration of the project. The main aims of this Task 6.1 are planning, conducting, and monitoring all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. Part of the Task’s work is the implementation of the communication strategy, including creation and, where required, updating and maintenance of branding and other digital and printed media (e.g., website, social media, campaign material, press kits).

SMARTSOL SIA leads this task and is responsible for planning, implementation, monitoring, and coordination of activities while the rest of the partners contribute to the plan, communication/dissemination activities, and reporting.

The project’s website and all promotional material will be updated throughout the lifetime of the project. It will display public information and the results of the project activities. Thus, D6.1 is related to all other tasks and deliverables of the project.

1.2 Document structure

This document provides an overview of the web portal (website) used for the public presentation, communication, and outreach of the iPROLEPSIS project as well as the project’s brand (logo), social media channels, and other communication tools. The deliverable is structured into two main parts: Section 1 initiates with the project’s introduction; Section 2 establishes the communication channels and tools.

2 iPROLEPSIS communication channels and tools

At the beginning of the iPROLEPSIS project, in months 1-3, an attractive, attention-grabbing and modern-looking brand and a corresponding website were developed to be used as a way to disseminate and communicate project’s information online.

2.1 Project’s brand identity

The iPROLEPSIS logo (**Figure 1**) is an easily recognisable (visual) identity of the project which depicts the title of the project combined with an attention-grabbing first letter that merges different colours. The overall image is forming a solid logo with imagery representative of healthcare theme, Arthritis’ purple ribbon, and smart innovations. These images are combining the content of the iPROLEPSIS project.

Figure 1 iPROLEPSIS logo

The project's colour palette corresponds with the project's logo colours and is used throughout the iPROLEPSIS' templates and dissemination material can be found in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 iPROLEPSIS colour palette

2.2 iPROLEPSIS public website

2.2.1 The aims of iPROLEPSIS website

The project's website aims to meet the following objectives throughout the lifetime of the iPROLEPSIS project and after it:

- Present the iPROLESIS towards external stakeholders, sharing the main objectives of the project, describing the information related to the development and also the results and the barriers to overcome;
- Connect with additional interested stakeholders which might lead to potential synergies and initiatives;
- Share information about the project's progress, the news from different dissemination activities, and public documents/deliverables;
- Provide access to the dissemination and communication material ('press kit') for consortium partners and interested stakeholders, allowing the download of project material and documents.

2.2.2 The features of iPROLEPSIS website

The web address (URL or a website domain) that was chosen for the project is www.iprolepsis.eu and the website is accessible by typing this address into the browser or a search engine. The website is setup within a flowing process, i.e., Home, About, Partners, News, Press Kit, and Contact Us sub-pages. It will be frequently updated with new input, e.g. news of the project, meetings, participation in events, blog, developments, etc. The website is also used to provide downloads of the dissemination material.

The website provides an easy and visually-attractive outlet for communicating the project's objectives and results to the wide audiences. Furthermore, social media to be used by the consortium (Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter) and newsletters as means of communication of the project is also presented in the following sections. The information provided at the web portal is an outcome of all iPROLEPSIS project partners' contributions.

The healthcare theme and the image of personal care are also highlighted by the background video of the website, which is displayed on the 'Home' page (Figure 3) and disappears by scrolling the website.

Figure 3 iPROLEPSIS website's Home page

The 'ABOUT' page in the iPROLEPSIS website lists the objectives of the project together with representative icons, displaying the seven key focuses of iPROLEPSIS objectives (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Seven objectives of iPROLEPSIS project displayed in the website

Furthermore, the 'HOME' page of the website allows for an easy subscription to the project's Newsletters (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5 Subscription to Newsletters part

The 'ABOUT' page on the iPROLEPSIS website lists the main facts of the project, and its primary objectives (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6 iPROLEPSIS' website's About section

The 'PARTNERS' page on the iPROLEPSIS website lists all partners in the project and displays their logos (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Project consortium partners' logos on the website

The 'NEWS' page of the iPROLEPSIS website displays the most recent project news, organised as separate articles. The news articles will be updated regularly and are organised chronologically (Figure 8).

Figure 8 Project News' section

The 'PRESS KIT' page of the iPROLEPSIS website (**Figure 9**) is the location where different dissemination and communication material is placed. The projects flyer, poster, and roll-up poster files are placed there for easy download.

Figure 9 iPROLEPSIS Press Kit

The 'CONTACT US' section of the iPROLEPSIS website provides an easy way to contact the consortium and submit questions and queries (**Figure 10**).

Figure 10 Contact Us for of the iPROLEPSIS website

2.3 iPROLEPSIS on social media

The iPROLEPSIS project’s social media accounts (**Figure 11**) – Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter – are linked with the iPROLEPSIS website and accessible by clicking the Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter icons on the project’s website. Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter accounts can be accessed using the ‘handle’ @iprolepsis. Social media account links can be found below:.

Social media channel	iPROLEPSIS link in the channel
LinkedIn	@iProlepsis
Twitter	@iprolepsis
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/iPROLEPSIS

Figure 11 iPROLEPSIS social media accounts

2.3.1 Social media posting guidelines

Tone and general notes that our consortium takes into account when posting in social media:

- Never post pictures or text containing confidential information from consortium's internal meetings;
- Use appropriate, inoffensive language (to ensure we get responses and stimulate debate);
- Be receptive to our readers' arguments – if we do not agree, we can defend our position without being rude;
- Gain/maintain credibility by sharing worthwhile, relevant content and show respect for other cultures and ideas, online as well as offline;
- We must be aware that libel and defamation laws apply;
- We created our project handle and use it consistently throughout the overall project implementation;
- If the partners, researchers, team members or other relevant organizations already have a strong, well established social media presence, we encourage them to communicate information about our project;
- Use handles, such as @HorizonEU and @EUfunded in our tweets and LinkedIn posts to maximise visibility and be recognized as part of the Horizon Europe community;

- Social media is becoming increasingly visual – we post pictures, videos or data visualizations to spark interest;
- Share images and tag other Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, to build a relationship with the audience and make them aware (the account tagged receives a notification) of content that might interest them, in the hope that they might want to retweet it.

2.4 iPROLEPSIS communication kit

At the beginning of the project, in months 1-3, a communication kit, including a project’s poster, flyer, and a roll-up poster were developed. These items reflect the project’s brand and present a summary of key information about the project. In **Figure 12** and **Figure 13** the iPROLEPSIS flyer and poster are presented, respectively.

Figure 12 iPROLEPSIS flyer

Figure 13 iPROLEPSIS poster

3 Conclusions

The format and contents of the iPROLEPSIS communication channels, including the website, are easily accessible to the public, easy to navigate, informative, and often used. The interlinked social media platforms provide fast and timely updates. All the information complies with the project’s Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement, Horizon Europe guidelines, and the European GDPR requirements. The website and the social media accounts provide therefore a good working basis for all iPROLEPSIS partners and support the project’s communication and dissemination goals.